
A Study On Livestock Trading Practices At Different Market Committees Of Satara District

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.16664908

Abstract:

The present study describes the buying and selling practices at 10 Agriculture Produce market committees of Satara district. The data for the present study is collected from 384 livestock traders with the help of thirteen parameters regarding trading practices. The collected data is analyzed with the help of various statistical methods such as mean. The study found that various types of livestock trading practices are performed by the livestock traders while trading the livestock, such as some agents/buyers wait at outside the market gate and approach the livestock sellers before letting him to enter in the market and does the transaction. It is because market committees charge 1% commission on the transaction value. The study is concluded with the expression that there should be inspection by the market committee officials to have fair livestock trading practices.

Keywords: *APMC, Livestock Trading Practices etc.*

Introduction:

The actions and procedures involved in the purchase, sale and exchange of livestock such as cattle, sheep, pigs, and poultry in agricultural markets are referred to as livestock trading practices. The movement of animals from producers to consumers is made easier by livestock trade procedures, which also influence market dynamics, profitability, and sustainability in the livestock sector. The researcher has used thirteen parameters to understand the livestock trading practices at market committees of Satara district. The five point scale ranges from strongly agree to strongly disagree to measure the response of sellers of different market committees. Livestock trading is a significant source of income and employment, especially in rural areas. Understanding its dynamics helps in designing policies and interventions that support and enhance these livelihoods.

Research in this area provides crucial insights for formulating effective trade policies at national and international levels, impacting export competitiveness and market access for livestock products. In essence, studying livestock trading practices provides a holistic understanding of a vital sector, allowing for evidence-based interventions and policies that promote economic growth, protect animal and public health, ensure social equity, and contribute to food security.

Objective of the Study:

- 1) To study the on livestock trading practices at different market committees of Satara district.

Research Methodology:

1. Data Required: Information is needed about the Agriculture Produce Market

Committee, infrastructure, marketing strategies, animal market structure, intermediary channels, etc.

2. Sources of Data: Both primary and secondary sources of data will be gathered for this project. A standardized questionnaire for gathering livestock information is used to gather primary data from buyers and sellers in the livestock market.

3. Sampling: There are 31 Agriculture Produce Market Committees in Satara District (10 primary and 21 sub-agricultural). Of the 31 existing Agriculture Produce Market Committees, 14 engage in the cattle trade. Livestock merchants trade their animals at the market yard once a week. All 14 Agriculture Produce Market

Committees were selected for the study. The census method is used to choose the APMC samples. Total 384 responses collected from livestock traders.

Analysis and Interpretation:

1. Livestock Buying Method:

It offers perceptions into the decision-making procedures, favored transaction channels, and preferences of buyers. With the use of this data, marketers may more efficiently manage resources, improve pricing structures, and better match the demands of their target audience. Furthermore, by comprehending the function of intermediaries, scholars may evaluate their influence on price transparency, market efficiency, and overall competitiveness.

Table No.1 Preferred Transaction Method by Livestock Buyers

Preferred transaction method	Name of APMC								Total Study Area
	Dahiwadi	Karad	Koregaon	Khandala	Phaltan	Satara	Vaduj	Wai	
Auction	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Middlemen	12 19.67	14 13.33	4 21.05	13 16.45	2 15.38	1 5	5 35.71	10 33.33	61 17.88
APMC	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Direct	49	91	15	66	11	19	9	20	280
Negotiation	80.32	86.67	78.95	83.54	84.61	95	64.28	66.66	82.11
Total	61 100	105 100	19 100	79 100	13 100	20 100	14 100	30 100	341 100

(Source: Compiled by researcher)

The above table describes the through whom the buyers prefer to purchase of animals in the market committee. It can be seen that 17.88% buyers prefer to buy the livestock from the middleman while 82.11% respondents buy the animals by the way of direct negotiation. 80.32% buyers from Dahiwadi market committee and 95% from Satara APMC buy the livestock by direct negotiations which are highest in all market committees of Satara district while 64.28% buyer from Vaduj market committee buys the animals from negotiation which is low as compared to the other market committees. On the other hand only 5% buyers of Satara

APMC prefer to buy the animals from the agents. Buyers from Vaduj and Wai market committees have the trust on the agents as highest number of buyers' trade with the help of middleman. No animal purchased and sold by auction in the market committee also market committee doesn't involve in the livestock transactions. The role of market committee is just to monitor the transactions.

2. Livestock trading practices at APMCs of Satara district:

Livestock trading practices are vital to agricultural economies. The scales such as strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree,

strongly Disagree have been used to measure the response. The data is collected from 384 livestock sellers to understand the livestock trading practices at different market committees of Satara district. In order to determine the total scores on the Likert scale, the frequency of each response option

was multiplied by the associated likert scale score. e.g. In respect of first statement, there are 325 strongly agreed responses from 384 livestock sellers. So total score is arrived as $325 \times 5 = 1625$. The percentage of each score is also calculated and stated below the score.

Table No. 2 Seller's response on livestock trading practices at APMCs of Satara district

SN	Statement	5	4	3	2	1	Total	Mean
1	Market committee avails more options/variety	1625 88.55	184 10.02	15 0.81	6 0.32	5 0.27	1835 100	4.78
2	An expert to determine the price of the animal	15 2.64	32 5.63	114 20.07	144 20.07	263 46.30	568 100	1.48
3	Wrongly deduction in livestock price	400 44	116 12.76	120 13.20	76 8.36	197 21.67	909 100	2.37
4	An inspector to monitor the transactions	360 45.39	40 5.04	66 8.32	94 11.85	233 29.38	793 100	2.07
5	Transactions only in cash	1525 85.91	180 10.14	45 2.53	12 0.67	13 0.73	1775 100	4.62
6	Market committee helps to raise money in credit transactions	270 33.54	108 13.41	111 13.78	100 12.42	216 26.83	805 100	2.10
7	Resolution of disputes by the Market Committee	660 58.20	144 12.69	135 11.90	48 4.23	147 12.96	1134 100	2.95
8	Realistic commissions by Intermediaries	185 24.89	72 9.69	153 20.59	110 14.80	223 30.01	743 100	1.93
9	Fair trade practices by intermediaries	210 27.34	76 9.89	159 20.70	106 13.80	217 28.25	768 100	2.00
10	Policy to return the animal after it has been sold	315 39.87	84 10.63	69 8.73	90 11.39	232 29.36	790 100	2.06
11	Additional charges are levied on transactions	910 66.66	236 17.28	69 5.05	60 4.39	90 6.59	1365 100	3.55
12	Follow up by the market committee	345 41.51	52 6.25	105 12.63	124 14.92	205 24.66	831 100	2.16
13	More complicated and time consuming transaction	1115 72.54	220 14.31	120 7.80	32 2.08	50 3.25	1537 100	4.00

(Source: Compiled by researcher)

The above table exhibits the livestock trading practices at various market committees of Satara district. The traders seek more options at market committees as the mean of this parameter is 4.78 which is highest among all parameters. 43.75% respondents agree with the statement that market committee resolves disputes promptly while 50.78% respondents don't think so. Others are neutral about this statement. 58.07% respondents are strongly

disagree with the statement that realistic commissions by Intermediaries while only 14.32 livestock sellers trust the livestock agents regarding the charge of commission. The mean of fair trade practices by intermediaries is 2 which is below average indicates unfair trade practices are performed by the intermediaries. 232 (60.41%) livestock sellers strongly agree that there is no policy to return the animal after it has been sold while only 84

respondents said that animal can be returned once it has been sold. 150 out of 384 respondents felt that no additional charges are levied on transactions in the market committees. The mean response of the parameter follow up by the market committee after trade takes place is 2.16 which is below average.

It is interpreted that the market committees at livestock markets do not appoint an expert to set the price of the animals. Rather, prices are decided by demand and market trends or through negotiations between buyers and sellers. This system depends on the knowledge of the participants and the state of the market and may result in price volatility. Intermediaries frequently charge exorbitant commissions at animal markets, which drastically lowers the revenues for farmers and sellers. This technique may put producers under financial strain, raise the price of cattle for consumers, and exacerbate inefficiencies in the market. To resolve this matter and safeguard the interests of all parties concerned, regulatory action is necessary by market committee to guarantee more equitable commission rates.

In livestock market committees, all transactions are conducted exclusively in cash. This means buyers and sellers exchange physical currency directly, without using digital payment methods or credit. This system ensures immediate payment and receipt for the livestock traded, simplifying the transaction process and avoiding potential delays associated with other forms of payment.

Findings:

1. Highest percentage of sellers (70.27%) prefers to sell their livestock to traders/businessman as most of the sellers bring sheep or goat in the market at Dadhiwadi Market committees. (Table No. 4.26)

2. Livestock selling price is kept secret from the middleman as 91.89% livestock sellers said that only agents know the exact selling price. (Table No. 4.28)
3. There is fixed market place available for trading at Malawadi market as APMC Dahiwadi has not owned land at that place. So market place changes from time to time. Livestock market is conducted where empty place is available.
4. The market starts before the sun rises (at 5 a.m.) and comes to an ends at 9 a.m. It is seen that 90% transactions takes place before 9 a.m.
5. It is seen that 51.69% livestock sellers believe that commission may be charged from 6% to 10% by the livestock agents. (Table No. 4.29)
6. According to 77.5% sellers, APMC staff monitors the transactions to control the unfair trade practices, also there are police personnel in the case of disputes.
7. In order to avoid to give transaction charges to market committee, some agents/buyers waits at outside the market gate and approach the livestock sellers before letting him to enter in the market and does the transaction. It is because market committees charge 1% commission on the transaction value.
8. It is seen that before buying the sheep or goat the buyer checks the size of the back by hand, taking into account its age and weight then offers the specific price.
9. Health of animals is not checked at the market place so buyers take the risk by anticipating the health, age, Milk yield etc.
10. It is observed that a trader who buys animals in large quantities cuts the hair on the legs or back of the goat

with a cloth as a mark or identification of the animal.

Suggestions:

1. 363 livestock traders out of 384 said that an expert is not appointed. Rather, prices are decided by demand and market trends or through negotiations between buyers and sellers. This system depends on the knowledge of the participants and the state of the market and may result in price volatility. So there should be an appointment of expert to determine livestock price to prohibit exploitation of farmers.
2. Market committees should establish proper dispute resolution mechanism to resolve disputes promptly. 50.78% livestock traders said that performance of committees to resolve grievances is not up to the mark.
3. Intermediaries frequently charge exorbitant commissions at animal markets as 58.07% livestock traders are strongly disagree with the statement that realistic commissions is charged by Intermediaries, which drastically lower the revenues for farmers and sellers. This technique may put producers under financial strain, raise the price of cattle for consumers, and exacerbate inefficiencies in the market. To resolve this matter and safeguard the interests of all parties concerned, regulatory action is necessary by market committee to guarantee more equitable commission rates.
4. There should be policy to return the animal after it has been sold. An animal can be returned once it has been sold. Since all sales are final, buyers must carefully check animals before making a purchase.
5. The mean of sellers response 2.16 and buyers response 2.06 suggests that no

proper follow up is taken by the market committee after trade takes place. At livestock marketplaces, market committees frequently neglect to follow up on deals, which can result in problems like unresolved disputes, a lack of transaction records, and diminished accountability. The cattle trading ecosystem's efficiency and confidence may be impacted by this oversight, which may cause buyers and dealers to become dissatisfied. Maintaining stakeholder confidence and maintaining market integrity need consistent follow-ups.

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